

Priming Nigerian Universities Graduates' Mindsets Towards National and Global Economic Participation, Competition and Development through Entrepreneurship Education

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ABSTRACT

Joblessness due, to shortage of job opportunities and lack of vibrant skills and competencies in business management necessitated the incorporation of Entrepreneurship Education (EE) along with the existing courses in Nigerian Universities by National University Commission (NUC) on the order of the federal government of Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the research. The population of the study comprised, the university graduates in Nigeria .The sample size of the study was One hundred and twenty (120) respondents selected, through a multi- stage sampling techniques. Three research question were raised for the study. Data was generated for the study through a self-structured research instrument by the research tagged "Questionnaire on Priming Nigerian Universities Graduates' mindsets towards Global Economics Participation, Competition and Development through Entrepreneurship Education ". It was fashioned on four likely rating scale of SA - strongly agreed, S - agreed, D - disagreed and SD - strongly Disagreed and rated four on (4) point ; 4,3,2 and , respectively. The research instruments were validated by two experts in test and measurement while, it reliability was determined through test retest method at two weeks interval. 0.70 Coefficient reliability was obtained data generated on the research questions were analyses using, descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counts, simple percentages and mean (7). Based on the result of the study conclusions were made that; EE could positively motivated universities graduates in Nigeria toward business creation and the government and development. Also, that EE could enable them to understand the work of business and economy nationally and internationally in Nigeria. EE would also burst their interest motivation toward involving in business on entrepreneurial activities. Recommendation were therefore made that, there should be a proper monitoring of the implementation of EE programme by the curriculum planners and developer. Also, universities graduate should be assisted by the government with a short- term loan so that they could overcome the challenges of source too the initial. Capital to start business activities from the conventional financial institutions.

Keywords: primitives, universities graduates ,mindsets competition, participation, development, entrepreneurship education

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707

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Graduates' of tertiary institutions unemployment constitutes part of major socio-economic challenges which governments at all level are contending with in the contemporary Nigerian society, today. Education is a human right, a mean to live a good standard of living and to achieve a sustainable development in all round perspectives. However the reality today is that graduate of tertiary institutions are seriously facing the problem of acute shortage of job opportunities in Nigeria. Erinsakini(2014), noted that graduates unemployment has risen because the Nigerian economy is not expanding at the rate which commensurate with the purpose of graduates from tertiary institutions and that most of the graduate fall into youth age bracket

Kwolfik(1998) stated that the youthful period is a critical one which has been noted as an essential time to gainfully engagemis them with jobs for decent confrontation with problems of poverty unemployment and lack of welfare packages by the government. today many youths which, a large number of them are tertiary institution graduate take solace and succor in crimes, such as prostitution,419 scam, internet fraudsters and hacking, armed robbery, stealing banditry, kidnappings, human rituals, oil theft, and lost. Several reason have been adduced to these unsavory trends and occurrences. One of the reason is lack of productive and vibrant skills in different vocations and entrepreuerical activities. Unfortunately for the nation based on the national population commission 2004, half of Nigeria population are under the age of 30 years thus, the nations, Nigeria's economy is predominantly a youthful one.

The National Universities Commission (NUC) (2004), reiterated that, there was massive disequilibrium between labour market requirement and lack of essential employable skills by the graduates deters youth and the entire development and economics growth of the country. (Diejomah and Orimolade,1991: Diabalem, oni and Adekola, 2001). This reality informed the federal Government in collaboration with national University commission(NUC) direction that all Nigerian Universities must establish Entreprenuership Development Centers (EDC), latest by 2007/2008 session

This directives seems to mark the bold step of Nigeria Universities to adopt drastic and sporadic action by designing curriculum in respect of entrepreneurship education (EE) along with the existing courses or programmes in the various Universities in Nigeria. further, the federal government of Nigeria set up a presidential committee on the introduction and implementation of entrepreneurship education (EE) in all tertiary institutions. The committee was saddled with the following responsibilities; curriculum review, promotion of the development and sustenance of entrepreneurship centres, promotion of science,, technology and innovation by providing incentives to students and lecturers, sensitization, advocacy and mobilization support for entrepreneurial education, programmes focus and finding. Sequel to the directive, many Nigerian Universities swing into action towards implementing the directives on the programme.

The section (1) of the Nigerian policy of Education FGN 2004, stated that the need for functional education to be relevant, practical that is capable to facilitate acquisition of

appropriate skills and the development of the society. By implication, it means the quality of instruction at all levels have to be diverted towards inculcating the values of acquisition of competencies necessary for self-reliance and poverty reductions. Further, EE is a tool for securing employment and emancipation of people through the provision and arguing of necessary knowledge and skills to make lives flourishing corroborating this, Daodu (2007), observed that.

Entrepreneurship Education is a strategy or instrument to channel the energies of University graduates in Nigeria away from paid employment.

Several studies had been conducted on Entrepreneurship Education and allied socio-economic challenges. As observed by the researchers studies have not been carried out on primary Nigerian University graduates mindsets towards global and national economic participation and development through Entrepreneurship Education. It was against this backdrop, the study was carried out.

Statement of the study

Joblessness and lack of vibrant practical skills' party have been attributed to poor standard of living thus, informing graduates involving in crimes in Nigeria. This identified challenge however, resulted into the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) in partnership with National Universities Commission (NUC) directives into incorporation of EE in addition with the existing programmes in Nigerian Universities. However, some lingering questions in minds are:

1. Has Entrepreneurship Education (EE) enable graduates of territory institutions in Nigeria to be active stakeholders in global and national economy?
2. Has EE equips graduates with vibrant, practical, functional and enterprising skills for participial in micro and macro businesses, and hosts?

It was against this background the research was conducted by the researchers.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The broad objective of the study was on primary Universities graduates mindsets towards national and global economic participation competition development through Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

1. Determine the impact of EE on graduates interest for global business activities;
2. Ascertain the influence of EE on graduates acquisition of competencies and skills venture into national economic sector; and
3. Investigate the input of EE on graduates orientation attitudes and motivation for both national and global entrepreneurial activities.

Research Questions

Three research questions were revised to guide the conduct of the study

1. EE impact on Universities graduates' interest towards global business activities?
2. Can EE influence graduates' acquisition of skills and competency to venture into a national economic sector?
3. EE has influence on graduates orientation, attitudes and motivation for business creation?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised graduates of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was used. The country, Nigeria was spitted into six geo-political regions (North, East, West, North-South, South West, South East and South-South). Then, from each of the regions, a star was purportedly picked based on population through a snow-bathing technique was used to Select Twenty (20) graduates of University to constitute the respondents for the study, thus, made the study population to be one hundred and twenty (120). Three research questions were raised for the study. Data was generated to the study through self-developed on structured research instruments tagged, “Questionnaire on Primary University Graduates. Mindsets towards National and Global Economic participation, completion development through Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria”. It was fashioned on Four-point Likert rating scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), rated on 4 points, 4. 3. 2 and 1, respectively. It was complemented with Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) that was used to elicit qualitative date for the study.

The research instruments were validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation while it reliability was determined through test-retest method, and 0.074 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data obtained on research question were analyzed using descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counts and mean). Data got through FGDs were collated, analyzed and transcribed, qualitatively.

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results

Presentation of Findings

Research Question One: Can EE impact on University graduates’ interests towards global business activities?

Table 1: Showing Simple Percentages, Frequency Counts and Mean (\bar{X}) on can EE impact on University graduates’ interests towards global business activities.

N= 120, C = 2.50								
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N %	Mean \bar{X}	Decision
1.	EE enables me to the international business environment	96 80	13 10.85	6 5	5 4.16	120	3.66	Accepted
2.	EE does not enable me to understand the global business environment	14 11.66	14 11.66	23 19.16	69 57.5	120	1.77	Rejected
3.	EE has enables me to venture	89	18	9	4	120	3.6	Accepted

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	into informational business activities.	74.16	15	7.5	3.33			
4.	EE has restricted me to national business, alone.	88 73.33	12 10	9 7.5	11 9.16	120	3.47	Accepted
5.	EE has opened my mind to productive and gainful international	6 5	7 5.83	11 9.16	96 80	120	1.35	Rejected
6.	Despite, EE that have acquired, I am yet to have an insight to gainful international business.	84 70	16 13.33	9 7.5	11 9.16	120	3.44	Accepted
	TOTAL WEIGHT	377 52.36	80 11.11	67 9.30	196 27.22		2.88	Accepted

N = Total Number of Respondents C = cut off Point

\bar{X} = Mean, SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, Strongly Disagreed

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 1 above, shows the results on research question one as following responses were obtained; 96 (80), 13 (10.83), 6 (5) and 5 (4.16) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (2), responses obtained indicate; 14 (11.66), 23 (19.16) and 69 (57.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item (3), responses got show 89 (74.16), 18 (15), 9 (7.5) and 4 (3.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. Also, item (4) reveals the following responses; 88 (73.33), 12 (10), 9 (7.5) and 11 (9.16) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

On item (5), the following responses were got; 6 (5), 7 (5.83), 11 (9.16) and 96 (80) for strongly agreed, Agreed, Strongly disagreed, Disagreed. In the same vein, 84 (70), 16 (13.33), 9 (7.5) and 11 (9.16) for strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed, disagreed.

For item (6), on a general note, the average rating scale of four which is $\bar{X} = 2.5$ is lesser than the mean of average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.88$), thus, indicates that EE has positive impact on University graduates' interests towards global business activities.

Research Question Two; Can EE influence graduates' acquisition of skills and competency to venture into a national economic sector?

Table 2: showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{X}) on can EE influence graduates' acquisition of skills and competency to venture into a economic sector.

N= 120, C = 2.50								
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N %	MEAN (\bar{X})	DECISION
7	EE enables me to carry out business planning.	102 85	6 5	7 5.83	5 4.16	120	3.70	Accepted
8	Despite knowledge acquired through EE, I can't still not be able to carry out business planning.	4 3.33	3 2.5	14 11.66	99 82.5	120	1.26	Rejected
9	EE helps me to know how to source for the initial capital to start business	94 78.33	16 13.33	4 3.33	6 5	120	3.65	Accepted
10	It is not EE acquired that enable me to know how to source for initial capital to start business	9 7.5	11 9.16	14 11.66	86 71.66	120	1.52	Rejected
11	EE helps me to know attributes of entrepreneurs	103 85.83	9 7.6	6 5	2 1.66	120	3.77	Accepted
12	It is not EE that enables me to know attributes of entrepreneurs	9 7.5	13 10.83	17 14.16	81 67.5	120	1.58	Rejected
13	EE enables me to know how to manage business, successfully	90 75	19 15.83	8 6.66	3 2.5	120	3.63	Accepted
14	EE does not make me to know how to manage business successfully	3 2.5	9 7.5	31 25.83	77 64.16	120	1.48	Rejected
	TOTAL WEIGHT	414 43.12	86 8.95	101 10.52	359 37.39		2.57	Accepted

Keys: N = Total Number of Respondents, C = Cut off points

\bar{X} = Mean, SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, Strongly Disagreed

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2 shows, responses obtained on research question two. On item (7), 102 (85), 6 (5), 7 (5.83) and 5 (4.16) were got for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (8), responses obtained indicate 4 (3.33), 3 (2.5), 14 (11.66) an 99 (82.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. 94 (78.33), 16 (13.33), 4. (3.33) and 6 (5) were results of responses that were got for strongly agreed,

agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed for item (9). Also, results obtained on item (10) show 9 (7.5), 11 (9.16), 14 (11.66) and 86 (71.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

On item (11), the following responses were got; 103 (85.83), 9 (7.6), 6 (5) and 2 (1.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. Also, obtained for item (12) were, 9 (7.5), 13 (10.83), 17 (14.16) and 81 (67.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (13), the following responses were got: 90 (75), 19 (15.83) 8(6.66) and 3 (2.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed.

Finally, on item (14), responses obtained indicate; 3 (2.5), 9 (7.5), 31 (25.83) and 77 (64.16) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

Generally speaking, the total weight result show that the average mean of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is lesser than the mean of average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.57$). Therefore, positively EE could influence graduates acquisition of skills and competency to venture into a national economic sector.

Research Question Three: Does EE has influence on graduates’ orientation, attitudes and motivation for business creation?

Table 3: showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{X}) on does EE has influence on graduates’ orientation, attitudes and motivation for business creation?

N= 120, C = 2.5 ⁰								
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N %	MEAN (\bar{X})	DECISION
15	EE has motivational effect on my interest in operating a small size business	92 76.66	18 15	9 7.5	1 0.83	120	3.67	Accepted
16	My desire to be operating a small size business has nothing to do with EE acquired in the University	6 5	2 1.66	13 10.83	99 82.5	120	1.27	Rejected
17	EE makes me to understand world of business, hence, primes my mind toward business creation after graduation from University	93 77.5	19 15.8	6 5	2 1.66	120	3.69	Accepted
18	I do not develop business enterprise because of EE that makes me to understand the	9 7.5	11 9.16	13 10.83	87 72.5	120	1.51	Accepted

	world of business							
19	EE enables me to know the importance of venturing into business for my economic self-reliance	103 85.83	7 5.83	4 3.33	6 5	120	3.72	Rejected
20	EE does not enable me to know the values EE to my economic self-reliance	1 0.83	5 4.16	15 12.5	99 82.5	120	1.23	Accepted
	TOTAL WEIGHT	304 42.22	62 8.61	60 8.33	294 40.83		2.51	Accepted

Keys: N = Total Number of respondents, C = cut off points, \bar{X} = mean, SA = Strongly Agreed, A = Agreed, D = Disagreed, SD = Strongly Disagreed.

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 3 above, shows results obtained on research question three. On item (15), 92 (76.66), 18 (15), 9 (7.5) and 1 (0.83) were obtained for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item (16), responses obtained show 6 (5), 2 (1.66), 13 (10.83) and 99 (52.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed and disagreed. On item (17), the following responses were got; 93 (77.5), 19 (15.83), 6 (5) and 2 (1.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item 18, responses obtained show 9 (7.5), 11 (9.16), 13 (10.83) and 87 (72.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, strongly disagreed, disagreed.

On item (19), the following responses were got; 103 (85.83), 7 (5.83) 4 (3.33) and 6 (5) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. Finally, on item (20), responses got were; 1 (0.83), 5 (4.16), 15 (12.5) and 99 (82.5) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

The total weight however, reveals that the average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.5$) is lesser than the mean of average rating scale of four ($\bar{X} = 2.51$), thus implies that EE, positively, has influence on University graduates' orientation, attitudes and motivation towards operating business or creation of business in Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The result on research question one was in consonance with the opinion of Erinsakin (2014) that EE incorporation and integration along with the existing courses on programmes in Universities in Nigeria had as one it objectives to expose students to the world of business. Further, to enable them to understand political, technological, social and local environments of business creation and development in the global, context.

The result was buttressed by some of the discussants during the FGD sessions.

I offered Entrepreneurship Education as an undergraduate student and offered the opportunity to understand the world of business and what business development entails.

A male graduates of sociology Enugu State in Nigeria FGD

In the same spirit, another discussant stated that;

Before I graduated from the University through EE programme, I had an extensive knowledge on some international businesses and on how is synergize or partnership with some international business agencies for business creation.

Female graduates of Botany in Oyo State, Nigeria- FGD

The result on research question two aligns also with the opinion of Daodu (2007), that Entrepreneurship Education is a strategy or instrument to channel the energies of Universities graduates in Nigeria towards business development rather, than, focusing on paid or government employment. The result is also buttressed by the submission. Arogbade and Chujoke (2010) that, EE programme will provide youths with insights into entrepreneurship and enterprise creation. Also, that it will enable youths to consider the option of starting a small business. By implication (EE) programme in Nigerian Universities graduates have enable many graduates to channel their energies towards business activities.

The result is also in consonance with the view expressed by some of the discussants during the FGDs.

If not that I offered EE as a course during my undergraduate days I would have venture into business.

A female graduates of Micro-Biology in Enugu State, Nigeria-FGD

Similarly, another discussant had this to say that:

Although, I am not Economic nor Business administration and Management student offering EE as a course that offered me a tip about economic and business sector before I graduated from University.

A male graduates of Mass Communication in River State, Nigeria – FGD

The result on research question three is also buttressed by Erinsakin (2014) that Entrepreneurship Education helps in inculcating values and competencies that will enable individuals in the society to be pro-active in business creation and small size enterprise management. Further, that through EE individuals could be motivated towards engaging in business activities. Osundele, Akingbade and Akinlabi (2012), opinion also aligns with the result that EE is very crucial at motivating people towards establishing or business creation. It can therefore be deciphered that EE programme in Nigerian Universities is planned, designed and implemented to give students values and skills for them to venture into business, thus, make them to overcome the psycho-social, economic and delinquencies associates with poverty and unemployment after graduating from the University.

The result was corroboratedly the submission of some discussants during the FDGs.

Acquisition of entrepreneurial values and culture is not incidental rather, knowledge acquired through EE as a course while was in the Univeristy.

A female graduates of Mathematics in Borno State, Nigeria – FGDs

Another discussant reiterated that:

Although I have not venture into business

However, through EE programme, I understand what it entails to start business and attributes of would be a successful entrepreneurs.

A male graduates of French in Niger State, Nigeria

Conclusion

Premised on the results of the research or study conclusions were made that Entrepreneurship Education enable the University graduates to be actively involved in business or entrepreneurial activities nationally and globally. Also, that EE has motivational effects on them towards venturing into business creation and also, assist the Universities graduates to understand the world of business, both at national ad global levels in Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made bases on the conclusion of the study;

1. EE programme implementation should be well monitored by the curriculum planners and developers in Nigeria.
2. Government should provide all the necessary logistics for the successful implementation of EE programme in Nigerian Universities.
3. The curriculum contents of EE programme should be more comprehensive than it is at present.
4. Graduates of Universities in Nigeria should be assisted with a short term loan to enable them to put training acquired through EE into practice. Also, to enable them to overcome the challenges of sourcing for the initial capital from the Conventional Financial Institutions to start business.
5. The universities graduates should be educated on the needs to put training, skills and knowledge acquired through EE into practice, especially, in reduction and self-reliance after graduating from the Universities.

References

- Arogundade, A.C. & Chijiok, K.J. (2010). Youths' unemployment: Entrepreneurship development programme as an interaction mechanism. Enugu: Institute for Development Studies, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus, Enugu State, Nigeria.
- Daodu, O. (2007), Entrepreneurship education: <http://www.isse2007.org/view.php>. Accessed 15th September, 2024.
- Diabelene, A., Oni, B & Adekola A. (2001). Labour market prospect for University graduates in Nigeria. Washinton D.C. World Bank.
- Diejomah, U & Orimolade, N. (1991). Unemployment in Nigeria: Economic and Social Sciences, 3:2, 127-132.
- Erinsakin, M.O. (2014). Impact evaluation of skill acquisition and entrepreneurial development training programmes in Ondo state, Nigeria. Unpublished thesis, Department of Adult and non-Formal Education: University of Ibadan.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, (2004). National economic empowerment strategy. Federal Ministry of Information and National Orientation; Abuja.
- National Universities Commission, (2004). Labour Market expectations of Nigerian, Abuja.
- Ogundele, O.L.K., Akingbade, W. A. & Akinlabi, H.M. (2012). Entrepreneurship training and education as strategic tool for poverty alleviation in Nigeria. American International Journal of Contemporary Records, 2:1-4.
- Woolfolk, A. (1988). Educational Psychology, 7th Edition. New York. Alliyat Baan.